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Experience and lessons of learning intervention programmes across the PAL Network members

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The analysis and arguments in the paper, as well as any errors, are the responsibility of the authors of the paper.

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Executive summary

The People's Action for Learning (PAL) Network is one of the leading South-South collaborations in education, working to improve learning outcomes in 14 countries across South Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, and Latin America.

This report provides an analytical overview of the learning interventions that PAL Network members have developed over recent years. These interventions share two common principles. First, they work from children's actual, rather than expected, learning levels. This is based on the approach most commonly known as Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL), which entails grouping children by current ability and using pedagogical approaches tailored to each group's level. Second, they treat education as a collective responsibility shared between citizens, communities, governments and school systems. Interventions work to bring these stakeholders together to view education as a collective responsibility that requires collective solutions.

Based on interviews and documentary analysis, in this report we focus on the four Network members with the most developed learning interventions to date:

- Pratham/ASER India's *Read India*
- MIA Mexico's *Summer Schools*
- ASER Pakistan's *Chalo Parho Barho*
- Jàngandoo Senegal's *Keppaaru Jàngandoo*.

While sharing common principles, each Network member has tailored their intervention programme according to the opportunities and constraints of their specific context. Consequently, the interventions differ in terms of:

- **Scale.** ASER India/Pratham and ASER Pakistan's interventions are already approaching national coverage. Jàngandoo Senegal tested the interventions in five provinces but aims to scale up to national level, while the Mexican model currently focuses on the state of Veracruz.
- **Government engagement.** ASER India and ASER Pakistan tend to work in cooperation with regional educational authorities to expand the model. Jàngandoo Senegal, which started with remedial interventions at the community level, has signed an agreement with the national government and seeks to have an impact in future national educational reform. In contrast, MIA Mexico's model works independently from educational policies and their decisions are based on community meetings.
- **Flexibility of the intervention model.** Whereas ASER India and ASER Pakistan have developed a standardized model of interventions in order to achieve larger scale reach in terms of the number of communities, schools and children reached, MIA Mexico's model is more flexible, typically developed in conjunction with community members and therefore adaptable. Once similarly flexible and locally adaptable, Jàngandoo Senegal is also now developing a more highly structured models in partnership with the national government in order to systematize remediation teaching in schools.

These adaptations to the given context can provide valuable lessons for organisations looking to implement similar TaRL interventions. In particular, Network members' experiences offer the following important considerations:

1. Learning assessment

- a. Assessments can help identify learning gaps and where the greatest need is, e.g. in terms of geography of education level
- b. Sharing assessment findings can help garner support for the intervention
- c. Assessments can evaluate both progress within interventions and their overall impact

2. Design and implementation

- a. It is essential to reflect on which stakeholder groups (e.g. teachers, citizens) will have the skills and motivations to implement the actions
- b. Longer term success can be boosted through partnership with communities and, where appropriate, government

3. Monitoring, Evaluation, Learning, and Sharing

It is important to tailor the monitoring systems and evaluations according to the needs of key audiences. For example:

- a. When viable, large scale quantitative data and/or randomized trials can help mobilize funding
- b. Small scale data can aid community engagement
- c. Recording and sharing instances of adaptation and improvement can help other organisations, supporting the long-term growth of effective learning interventions.

Introduction

The People's Action for Learning (PAL) Network is arguably the leading South-South international collaboration in education. The Network brings together organisations in fourteen countries, across three continents, working to assess the basic reading and numeracy competencies of all children, in their homes, through annual citizen-led assessments.

Diversity is key to understanding the dynamics of the PAL Network. Although citizen-led assessments have many commonalities, they also differ significantly, and part of the purpose of this research is to capture these differences and the reasons for them. Members are diverse in backgrounds, history with citizen-led assessments and in their evolutions from assessment to action.

Network members have already leveraged this diversity in their move from assessment to action. More established PAL members have supported other members in the implementation of direct interventions. For instance, Pakistan drew lessons from Pratham/ASER India's experience and followed a very similar path while still adapting to the particularities of its own context. There are a variety of action models among PAL members, but a key principle across the network is to understand and work from where children actually are with learning, not where they purportedly should be.

The role of this current report is to explore some of the key actions that are already taking place within the Network. It focuses on direct pedagogical interventions (both in and out of school) that seek to change teaching and learning approaches by identifying and working from children's actual, rather than expected, learning levels. In particular, it considers the following learning interventions from four countries: Pratham/ASER India's Read India, ASER Pakistan's Chalo Parho Barho, MIA Mexico's Summer Schools, and Jàngandoo Senegal's Keppaaru Jàngandoo.

The analysis that follows is based on a combination of interviews with PAL Network members, participation in PAL Network events, and documentary analysis. Members of the research team held two individual interviews each with ten of the Network's country members, as well as an interview with the PAL Network Secretariat. Members of the research team attended the PAL Network's annual meeting in Mexico, March 2017, and held a workshop focused on the current project in Uganda, May 2018, which was attended by the Secretariat and representatives from each of the ten participating Network countries. Documentary analysis was undertaken on a combination of published and grey literature provided by PAL Network members. The documentary resources that we draw upon to understand the respective countries' interventions are listed in the References section at the end of this report.

Research questions for the comparison of cases:

A key driver of the global growth of citizen-led assessments was the willingness of PAL Network members to share their expertise with new and prospective country teams. Similarly, as the Network shifts from assessment to action, there is much to be learned from the experiences of members and their efforts to establish direct learning interventions. This report seeks to contribute to this effort by addressing the following questions:

1. Where across the Network have learning interventions already been implemented?
2. How have Network members adapted learning intervention models according to their own contexts?
3. What can other Network members learn from these experiences to maximize the impact of their own learning intervention programmes?

1. Where across the Network have learning intervention models been implemented?

The ultimate intended outcome of citizen-led assessments is improved learning outcomes. Different PAL Network members have implemented learning interventions to improve the low results detected in their assessments. While the form of intervention varies from one country to another, the key, crosscutting trend is to target teaching according to the basic skill level of the child.

Table 1: Summary of learning interventions by country

	Name	Established	Scale
India <i>ASER India</i>	Read India	2007	National. In 2016-17, over 20,000 villages
	Lakhon mein Ek	2015	National, 28 states, 150,000 communities
	Teacher training partnerships	2015	13 states (about 95 District and State Institutes of Education and Training (DIETs))
Mexico <i>Medición Independiente de Aprendizajes (MIA)</i>	Summer schools	2017	Pilot: 3 summer schools. School interventions: 9 primary schools, 2 preschools, 1 secondary school and a baccalaureate institution
Pakistan <i>ASER Pakistan</i>	Chalo, Parho, Barho camps	2011	Three provinces: Sindh, Baluchistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa
Senegal <i>Jàngandoo</i>	Keppaaruu Jàngandoo.	2016	First stage (community): 1480 students. Second stage (in school): two regions but remediation in schools 9,000 children

In this report, we focus on four of the network members – ASER India, MIA Mexico, ASER Pakistan, and Jàngandoo Senegal – with the most developed learning intervention models. Table 1 summarises learning interventions currently being carried out by these four members. These interventions build upon a teaching model developed by Pratham, the umbrella organisation of ASER India. Core elements of this approach, known both as TaRL (Teaching at the Right Level) and as CAMaL (Combined Activities for Maximized Learning), include:

1. establishment of level-wise groups
2. explicit learning goals for each group
3. tailored teaching techniques
4. periodic tracking of progress (Banerji & Duflo, 2015)

Points 2, 3, & 4 have been retained across all of the countries' interventions. The major point of difference across the countries to date is point 1, the establishment of level wise groups. For example, MIA Mexico and Jàngandoo Senegal do not separate children into level-wise groups. Jàngandoo Senegal, for instance, does not fix a priori goals for the interventions. Both Jàngandoo Senegal and MIA Mexico have flexible instead of systematized progress tracking.

The comparison of a few examples will help readers to understand how network members have designed and implemented their interventions according to their own contexts following different processes and paths to adapt to their corresponding circumstances.

India

Pratham's Read India uses the Combined Activities for Maximized Learning (CAMaL) approach in its interventions in learning camps and libraries. These interventions reached more than 20,000 villages and communities between 2016 and 2017.

Children participating in a Read India intervention. December 2017. Source: Pratham Education Foundation.

Pratham works within the public education system and has partnerships with local authorities in order to enhance Read India's learning interventions. The next stage of interventions in camps (Read India Plus) aims to equip children with the ability of 'self-learning through group-learning' in order to eliminate or reduce teacher-driven learning, and sustain improved learning outcomes.

In addition, Pratham have developed a community mobilisation programme, called Lakhon mein Ek. Over four months, this programme supported community members to assess their own children and implement learning interventions based on the Read India methodology.

Pratham also works with the public education system to spread its interventions through a training programme for CAMaL teachers in India conducted by official educational institutes at the local or national level called DIETs (District Institutes of Education and Training) and SCERT (State Council of Educational Research and Training). In this programme, the control of the interventions is transferred from Pratham to government staff to teachers. Pratham's team trains teacher trainers (4–6 days); these teacher trainers then conduct practice classes (15–20 days); they then train government schoolteachers (4–6 days); and finally schoolteachers teach children.

Pakistan

The Chalo Parho Barho programme begins its interventions by identifying children (aged 6 – 12 years) who are out-of-school or at risk of dropping out. Chalo Parho Barho's remedial literacy/numeracy camps enrol more than 20,000 out-of-school children and mainstream them after 45 days into the identified schools using school admission tests.

The camps have also worked with 13,000 in-school primary school children in grades 3–5 who are behind in basic literacy and numeracy skills. The learning camps help them attain grade appropriate knowledge and skills in order that they stay in school. Chalo Parho Barho has hired and trained around 600 'para teachers' and 1,500 government teachers and district officials.

Mexico

Medición Independiente de Aprendizajes (MIA) interventions are directed to schools in municipalities where most children do not attain the right level corresponding to their school grade, as determined by household assessments.

Summer Schools was a pilot educational intervention in basic education schools to improve mathematical and reading skills. The methodology of MIA Plus, which was used in the pilot, was also employed in school and community interventions that took place during the school year 2016/2017. MIA Plus was also used during interventions that took place in libraries and a few primary schools in the city of Tuxtla; these were called, 'The Magic of Letters'.

To date, MIA's programmes in the state of Veracruz include:

- Summer schools
- In-school interventions
- Community initiatives (these combine in and out of school programmes but are implemented by local community members directly instead of MIA volunteers)
- Out of school educational programmes in Xalapa (mainly in libraries)

Senegal

The remediation initiative Keppaar Jàngandoo (Under the shadow of Jàngandoo) began after assessments found that the majority of primary school children had low levels of foundational literacy and numeracy. Jàngandoo developed tools for household support and used community-based remedial activities in the first stage of intervention and in-school remediation in the second stage. Although the implementation of remedial actions was not systematic initially, the model has been adapted and structured following clear steps.

With inspiration from Pratham/ASER India's Combined Activities for Maximized Learning (CAMaL) approach, the initiative consists of the following core elements:

- Remedial learning programmes
- Teacher training
- Forming three-way partnerships with local authorities and the academic inspectorate to further develop pedagogy and learning materials

Following a partnership with UNICEF and PAGE (Programme d'Amélioration de la Gestion participative de l'Ecole – Programme for Improving Participatory School Management), the goal is now to implement the programme within schools, through the Programme for the Betterment of Reading and Geometry. The partnership met with education ministers in December 2017 to discuss the expansion of the intervention at the national level.

2. How have network members designed the learning intervention according to their own contexts?

Before exploring and comparing models of members' learning interventions, it is useful to consider three structural elements on which they differ:

1. **Scale.** ASER India/Pratham and ASER Pakistan's interventions are already approaching national coverage. Jàngandoo Senegal tested the interventions in five provinces but aims to scale up to national level, while the Mexican model currently focuses on a specific region.
2. **Government engagement.** ASER India and ASER Pakistan tend to work in cooperation with regional educational authorities to expand the model. Jàngandoo Senegal, which started with remedial interventions at the community level, has signed an agreement with the national government and seeks to have an impact in future national educational reform. In contrast, MIA Mexico's model works independently from educational policies and their decisions are based on community meetings.
3. **Flexibility of the intervention model.** Whereas ASER India and ASER Pakistan have developed a standardized model of interventions in order to achieve larger scale reach in terms of the number of communities, schools and children reached, MIA Mexico's model is more flexible, typically developed in conjunction with community members and therefore adaptable. Once similarly flexible and locally adaptable, Jàngandoo Senegal is also now developing a more highly structured models in partnership with the national government in order to systematize remediation teaching in schools.

These elements have significant implications for each country member's (1) use of assessment data, (2) design of interventions, (3) implementation strategy, and (4) MELS (Monitoring, Evaluation, Learning, and Sharing).

Use of assessment

Identifying need. One commonality is that the results of the larger citizen led assessments are used when making decisions about the targeting of these pedagogical interventions. For instance, Pratham/ASER India uses estimates from the ASER report, which suggest that 50 million children in grades 3 to 5 have fallen behind expected curriculum levels. This has led Pratham/ASER India to focus interventions on the middle primary school years, and in those states with the lowest learning levels. Jàngandoo Senegal's citizen-led assessment has helped them to identify which of the country's regions they will prioritise.

Buy-in. Assessment data also serves an important role in initiating each intervention. In Pakistan, community meetings are held to disseminate the results of the household survey, the ASER report, and to convince the community of the need to send out of school children to school. ASER Pakistan's umbrella organisation, Idara-e-Taleem-o-Agahi (ITA), works with the government to identify out-of-school children located in villages with low performing school districts.

Conversely, MIA Mexico works with volunteers and stakeholders to decide how to use the assessment data and which learning interventions to conduct. In Senegal, the discussion of assessment data within the community and their reactions are key factors in the process as sharing the data with households is considered as a first stage of their remediation programme.

Pratham/ASER India's grassroots Lakhon mein Ek campaign prioritises citizen mobilisation through assessment efforts. It helps communities gain ownership of the process by entrusting them with crucial elements of the assessment itself, such as the data collection. Villagers collect and discuss data in this campaign, which involves state and district level partners, teacher training institutes, colleges/universities, schools and NGOs.

Why do we need this campaign?

Village Poster from Lakhon mein Ek Campaign. Source: Pratham India.

Learning assessment in Senegal 2017. Source: Lartes-Ifan

Learning assessment in Pakistan during ASER Pakistan training 2015. Source: ITA.

Within interventions. Assessments are also used within each country's learning interventions. For MIA Mexico and Jàngandoo Senegal, these primarily take the form of baseline and endline assessments. Jàngandoo Senegal uses an assessment tool at baseline to identify the children in greatest need of support, and the areas of learning in which they need remediation, while an endline assessment measures the progress made by the children. MIA Mexico discusses these baseline and endline results with parents, school boards and members of the municipality. In addition, volunteers submit a detailed report about aspects of the learning progress that pays attention to individual cases. In addition, ASER Pakistan and Pratham/ASER India use assessments during interventions, partly to understand how well the given intervention is working, partly to identify individual children's progress and regroup them into ability levels accordingly. This takes place at specific periods of 15, 30 and 45 days

Intervention design

Focus. The focus of the intervention varies across the countries. Most PAL Network members focus on children aged 8- to 10-years old, but MIA Mexico works with the broader age range of 5–15 years. In Senegal, in-school remedial interventions are conducted at the primary school level but older children have also participated in community interventions.

Typically, interventions focus on improving arithmetic and reading skills, as in Pakistan and India. Meanwhile, MIA Mexico and Jàngandoo Senegal prefer to prioritise one subject over the other. For instance, some summer schools in Mexico preferred focusing solely on helping children reach acceptable levels of mathematic skills while others, such as an out-of-school intervention called The Magic of Letters focus on improving reading skills. Jàngandoo Senegal has dedicated considerable efforts to remedial training for teachers and learning materials focused on French and Arabic learning difficulties. Jàngandoo Senegal's own assessment has revealed these subjects to be the weakest for many students yet current learning interventions in schools dedicate two hours per week to maths and two hours to reading.

Learning tools. The learning tools developed by PAL Network members are adaptable to each context. Pratham/ASER India has primarily developed its learning tools internally, using an iterative process to test and refine tools within its interventions over time. In Mexico, Centro de Investigaciones y Estudios Superiores en Antropología Social (CIESAS) and the University of Veracruz developed MIA's own learning support materials using didactic tools such as Circles of Literary Expression, Peer Tutoring, and Bancubi. For Jàngandoo Senegal, LARTES developed remedial textbooks in Arabic and French that can be used by parents at home and by teachers in schools.

Duration. The duration of learning interventions varies from country to country. In India and Pakistan the activities take places in intensive learning camps several times during the school year, typically for 45 days each. In Mexico, some interventions are developed in 20 sessions with out-of-school interventions taking place on consecutive days and school interventions at a different frequency. In Senegal, once sporadic remedial learning programmes now take place consistently for four hours per week during normal school hours over the whole year.

Implementation strategy

Partnerships. A common theme across the learning interventions is that education is a collective responsibility. If these interventions acknowledge that people's voice is critical for holding governments accountable for educational outputs (GEM report 2017), then the distribution of collective responsibility and collaboration of stakeholders must also adapt to scale and context.

In its interventions, Pratham/ASER India works primarily with community volunteers, particularly mothers, but also government schoolteachers and local authorities. While these entities cooperate in implementing of Read India, agreements with local and district authorities remain central. Lakhon mein Ek reflects a desire to encourage more direct action among community members. Pratham/ASER India's efforts to influence within-school teaching practices are visible in teacher training programmes focused on state- and district-level partnership, working primarily with the State Council of Educational Research and Training (or SCERT) and at the district level with the District Institutes of Education and Training (or DIETs).

ASER Pakistan's learning camps involve the local community, including parents, management committee, teachers/head teachers and para teachers. Provincial and district governments request Chalo Parho Barho camps which ITA and other organizations implement for in-school and out-of-school children in low performing areas. When reflecting about building educational practice ASER Pakistan engages varied stakeholders, including government officials, at both regional and national level.

In Mexico, local churches, district government authorities, civil society organizations and educational institutions, with the help of state and local partner organisations, are involved in deciding the organization of the learning interventions. The flexibility of the Mexican model aims to allow parents, communities, students and staff to shape and directly monitor school policies and practices.

Learning interventions have further been put in place by Jàngandoo Senegal's partnerships with organizations such as UNICEF and PAJE (Plateforme d'accompagnement des Jeunes de Senegal – Platform for Supporting Senegalese Youth) and also entered into a three-way agreement with LARTES-IFAN, local authorities and academy inspectorates. Engaging local communities also remains central to Keppaaruu Jàngandoo, which defines itself as a partnership between citizens and decision-makers at the national and local level searching for solutions to helping children learn better.

Training. As the country with the longest history of working on learning interventions following citizen-led assessment data, Pratham/ASER India developed a specific teacher's training programme after signing agreements with national and district education institutes. Pratham/ASER India's teacher training programme is conducted in partnership with SCERTs and DIETs. Meanwhile, ASER Pakistan hires para-teachers and schoolteachers who are recruited and trained by ITA in the Combined Activities for Maximized Learning (CAMAL) methodology to conduct Chalo Parho Barho camps in local government schools.

Training of para-teachers in DI KHAN. 2018. Source ITA Pakistan

MIA Mexico trains volunteers to use the MIA Plus methodology. These volunteers are either university graduates who participated in MIA assessments or people who belong to a partner women's civil society organisation. MIA Mexico does not train schoolteachers, but school boards and teachers decide which school classes would benefit the most from MIA volunteers support.

Training of facilitators. "Medicion Independiente de Aprendizajes. Mi experiencia en MIA". 2016. Source: Ichan Tecolotl-Ciesas Mexico.

In Senegal, the training has focused mainly on school teachers but community volunteers have also been trained to implement remediation activities for children in local spaces. These include children from the lowest learning levels (what Jàngadoo identifies in the baseline assessment as group 1; children who can hardly identify words). Jàngadoo Senegal has now joined a partnership with national and regional government to spread remedial teacher's training programmes.

Training of remediation team members 2016. Source LARTES IFAM Senegal

MELS (Monitoring, Evaluation, Learning, and Sharing)

Impact. Read India/CAMaL has produced significant learning improvements in reading and basic arithmetic for children. Pratham's teacher training programmes at the state level (SCERTs) and at the district level (DIETs) have also received positive feedback. Several SCERTs and DIETs requested repeat intervention with a second batch of students in the next year. Community based activity groups in libraries also have contributed in creating a reading environment in the communities that encourages children's sustained learning. Additionally, Pratham's reports about the Lakhon mein Ek campaign confirmed that it was possible to mobilize people on a mass scale (150,000 communities in 4 months), encourage them to understand a problem and participate in actions to solve it, i.e. move from assessment to action.

Steps to help community members improve learning levels in their villages. Village Poster English of Lakhon mein Ek Campaign. Source: Pratham India.

ASER Pakistan's Chalo Parho Barho is credited with improving the learning outcomes of children in grades 4 and 5 who were at risk of dropping out. Recent results from the programme (ITA, 2015 & 2017) showed learning gains for children in underperforming districts of Sindh, Punjab, Balochistan and in KP (Khyber Pakhtunkhwa). Increased enrolment in the programmes and community mobilization are the direct results of these interventions.

End line assessments of MIA Mexico's interventions (MIA, 2017) also show progress in participating children and the reports from trained volunteers are positive. Interventions taking place in community libraries have helped encourage communities take the ownership of children's learning, an observation made in libraries in India and Mexico.

An early and positive outcome of Jàngandoo Senegal's learning interventions was the availability of new learning materials for parents and teachers in two languages. Also teachers obtained new materials and digital support. End line assessments and recent reports show important learning gains, which the government has considered as evidence to support an expansion of the interventions (Lartes-Ifan 2017).

External. Read India has completed frequent and rigorous work in external evaluations. Working in partnership with J-PAL, Read India has evaluated the impact of its interventions using randomised controlled trials (see, for example, Banerjee et al. 2007, 2010, 2016). For an external evaluation of the teacher's training programme Pratham/ASER worked with IDinsight, an international organisation with experience in conducting evaluations on education programmes.

In Pakistan, ITA commissioned an impact evaluation research team to conduct a rigorous evaluation to measure the impact of its learning interventions in rural areas.

In Senegal, an external evaluation in 2016 assessed the impact of interventions on children who attended remediation courses in Malicounda and Rufisque–East. LARTES also organized a national review day, inviting relevant stakeholders involved in remediation in each intervention area. These included the local authority, education and training inspectorate, remediation staff and focal points. LARTES and the National Educational Inspection are now in charge of evaluating both the intervention process and the learning outcomes.

Internal. In contrast, MIA Mexico's interventions do not undergo such processes of external feedback and evaluations. Rather the focus of MIA Mexico is to adapt to the needs and demands of local communities while building and creating a social consciousness that promotes community participation and educational progress. Consequently, MIA Mexico has attached greater value to internal assessment, which consists of an in-depth end line assessment at the end of the interventions and meetings at the level of local communities to communicate these assessments.

For the moment, only Pratham/ASER India and ASER Pakistan have been able to measure their programme reach, changes in attendance, community engagement and children's learning in a clear and systematic way. This applies also to Pratham/ASER India's tracking of teachers training to understand whether they do in fact end up teaching and if so, whether they recall and use Pratham's teaching-learning methodology.

ASER Pakistan's internal assessment includes the use of monitoring forms, including random tests, which are compiled by a district Chalo Parho Barho officer, then entered into a database. This effort is coordinated by District Managers who report concerns to a Head office. Additionally, for the duration of this programme ASER Pakistan relies on the guidance and expertise of an External Research Fellow who observes all activities and material development stages but also assists in looking at the data received and performing statistical analysis to measure and gauge the impact at the ground level.

Future goals

Expansion. ASER Pakistan seeks to influence the government's education policy strategy to make it include their proposed solutions. Another expansion strategy is to make all of the intervention materials available to other organisations interested in implementing the same approach. In the coming two years, ASER Pakistan will train two other organizations to implement the model in new districts and provinces.

Keppaaru Jàngandoo has attained financing from Dubai Cares to systematize internal evaluation as it expands its programme across three regions. The model has specific and clear targets: 43,200 children, including 720 teachers; 152 remediation officers; and 24 academic inspectors for the monitoring. It intends to use the same core remedial model with adaptations for each region. In combination, with the initial programme and this expansion are projected to reach a third of targeted children in Senegal.

MIA Mexico will continue to work within Veracruz to expand the number of interventions in the multiple towns/villages within municipalities where it has already done interventions. In these municipalities there exists a large number of low-income villages where the need of interventions is urgent. Rather than seeking to scale up to a national or federal level, MIA Mexico's focus is on encouraging replication from similar organisations through a collaborative network of volunteers and local organizations.

The Lakhon mein Ek initiative expanded elements of the Read India programme to a near nationwide scale. Looking forward, the major focus is on the model's sustainability rather than its ongoing growth. One element of this is to transfer greater responsibility to communities, which is a key focus of Lakhon mein Ek. Another is to encourage greater involvement from teachers and school leaders at the village/community level, an intervention which Pratham/ASER India is currently piloting through a research partnership with the REAL Centre at the University of Cambridge.

Pratham/ASER India and ASER Pakistan's pedagogical materials and process documentation are packaged and available for others to use and replicate. MIA is successfully linking to other local community initiatives and supporting them in adapting their processes to the on-going changing needs of these communities.

Adaption. READ India's implementation model of the programme has evolved constantly since its inception. Key changes typically have taken place over a three-year cycle with the programme having been divided into four broad phases based on its evolution over the years.

For example, Pratham/ASER India's teacher training model has also made some adaptations from the initial cycle. For its second cycle (2017/2018) it modified the design of the programme in terms of scale. Due to uncertainties in some institutes' academic calendar and shorter duration of field practice sessions for implementation of learning camps, the number of states was reduced and the teaching-learning module with learning camp (assessment to action) was offered as the main intervention. Many small changes to training structure and content were made based on the recommendations of the external evaluation.

ASER Pakistan has also evolved and, like the India and Senegal cases, also seeks to impact national policy. Until now it has been funded by international donors but the aim is to become part of a set of responses to improving education outcomes paid for through provincial education budgets. The short-term objective in 2017 was that at least one provincial government would have agreed to include resources or Chalo Parho Barho in poor performing districts in their annual budgets.

ASER Pakistan's Chalo Parho Barho camps are looking forward to implementing an adaptation related to teachers. Until now, Chalo Parho Barho has been led by para-teachers hired from the local community and paid on a monthly basis by the implementing partner. For the future, Chalo Parho Barho proposes to engage university students (as opposed to para-teachers) trained on accelerated learning methodology to lead the learning camps in exchange for course credits. Potentially, this would bring down the cost of the programme significantly in the short run and make it sustainable at the district level in the long run.

Some examples of adaptations that Jàngandoo Senegal are making include: focusing the programme to work in schools on a second stage rather than in communities as was the case in the first interventions; providing their own training to volunteers working in the interventions; and focusing the great majority (80%) of resources on children in the first school grade, i.e. age 7–8.

MIA Mexico has decided to eliminate out of school interventions during the school year because they have not worked well. They are now focused on summer camps since communities and parents prefer interventions when parents need to work but children are on holidays and thus able to participate in the interventions more consistently.

3. What can other Network members learn from these experiences to maximize the impact of their own learning interventions?

Table 2: Summary of variations across the learning interventions of PAL members selected case studies

	Use of assessment	Design	Implementation	MELS (Monitoring, Evaluation, Learning, Sharing)	Future goals
India <i>ASER India</i>	Based on National curriculum	Intensive learning camps (after school hours) for children grouped according to their level after assessment	Large scale (vast number of participants: children and schools) Community participation promoted by ASER but decisions need agreements from national and district educational authorities	Systematic internal evaluation and external rigorous controls	Sustainability of community-led model, expansion of practices into schools
Mexico <i>Medición Independiente de Aprendizajes (MIA)</i>	Assessment tool includes extra-curricular learning issues	Summer learning camps and community interventions (libraries) where all interested families can -enlist their children. Interventions in school with entire classes but helping children with individualized attention and materials	Implemented at small scale in a small number of schools and community centres. Programme design decisions depend on MIA and on direct community stakeholders	On going internal but flexible evaluation and feedback by direct stakeholders. No immediate plans for external evaluation.	Increase moderately and gradually the geographic scope of the interventions. Finding local social agents that could be local partners
Pakistan <i>ASER Pakistan</i>	Based on National curriculum Focused on out of school and at risk of drop out children	Intensive learning camps for children grouped according to their level after assessment	Large scale (vast number of participants: children and schools) in the provinces of Sindh, Baluchistan and Punjab. Community participation promoted by ITA but decisions need National and district educational authorities agreements	Both external and internal evaluations (similar to India)	To attract funding support from regional government budgets
Senegal <i>Jàngandoo</i>	Based on national curriculum Now focused on spotting the deficiencies of educational system at national level at within primary schools	Initially, community interventions and household remediation help. In its new iteration, the focus is on school interventions	Implemented first in five provinces with direct participation of community agents and households. Progressing into more school boards and local –national government participation as programme is scaled up and cover the whole country.	Internal (monitoring through digital application), and external evaluation by LARTES and National Education Inspectorate	Drive the national educational system towards reforms that will improve learning

Comparing the ways in which Pratham/ASER India, ASER Pakistan, Jàngandoo Senegal and MIA Mexico have developed their learning interventions can allow other PAL Network members to maximize the impact of their own adaptations of learning intervention programmes.

Each PAL network organization must reflect and plan a strategy for future learning interventions according to its principles. In doing so, the organizations must bear in mind that a grassroots community-based model has different considerations than a model seeking to develop interventions in cooperation with national or regional education authorities and policymakers.

Grassroots interventions that call for working closely with local civil society organisations, for example, tend to focus on small-scale projects that do not depend on a big public budget or on international donor support. These types of projects use flexible and tailor-made follow-up mechanisms that allow local agents to actively participate and monitor the actions at all times. In contrast, PAL Network members seeking to develop intervention models at large scale will likely require support from the relevant government authorities (possibly at multiple levels) to implement their action. As a consequence, they will also tend to need a more prescriptive intervention model using more standardized monitoring mechanisms and control.

That said, the PAL Network's learning interventions to date share a range of principles, which can help guide future efforts across the Network and beyond for implementing reforms aimed at raising learning, particularly for those children who are most at risk of being left behind:

1. Learning assessment

- a. Assessments can help identify learning gaps and where the greatest need is, e.g. in terms of geography of education level
- b. Sharing assessment findings can help garner support for the intervention
- c. Assessments can evaluate both progress within interventions and their overall impact

2. Design and implementation

- a. It is essential to reflect on which stakeholder groups (e.g. teachers, citizens) will have the skills and motivations to implement the actions
- b. Longer term success can be boosted through partnership with communities and, where appropriate, government

3. Monitoring, Evaluation, Learning, and Sharing

It is important to tailor the monitoring systems and evaluations according to the needs of key audiences. For example:

- a. When viable, large scale quantitative data and/or randomized trials can help mobilize funding
- b. Small scale data can aid community engagement
- c. Recording and sharing instances of adaptation and improvement can help other organisations, supporting the long-term growth of effective learning interventions.

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